

METHODS OF LEARNING ENGLISH FOR INTERMEDIATE LANGUAGE LEARNERS

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Abstract: Here we talk about problems and solutions for beginners, not just for intermediate language learners, but for learners of all levels. Also, methods for independent preparation are shown to the intermediate level learner.

Keywords: first mistake, intermediate learner, Pimsler method, Schechter method, Petrov method, Dragunkin method, 14000 words

Аннотация: Здесь мы говорим о проблемах и решениях для начинающих, не только для изучающих язык на среднем уровне, но и для изучающих все уровни. Также обучающимся среднего уровня показаны методы самостоятельной подготовки.

Ключевые слова: первая ошибка, обучающийся среднего уровня, метод Пимслера, метод Шехтера, метод Петрова, метод Драгункина, 14000 слов.

Introduction:

Nowadays, learning English has become the need of the hour. because of this, the majority of the people of the world use the English language to work with other foreign countries. English is needed not only for development in one field, but also for representatives of many fields. A person who wants to achieve success in his field should know foreign news in order not to be left behind. for this you need to know foreign language. It is known that the international language is English.

Everyone has difficulties in learning a foreign language. For example, memorizing words, grammar, correct pronunciation. Everyone has problems, but

everyone has a different solution. Our first mistake is that we force ourselves to learn. First of all, we have to learn with a little desire. When memorizing vocabulary, you should not use simple methods, that is, it is not right to memorize the same word 3 times, you should develop visualization, learn grammar from several books, not from one book, pay attention to the mistakes in pronunciation, and practice pronunciation. Basic skills for an intermediate language learner. A student of this level should be able to use the language easily, be able to tell about his work or events, dreams, wishes, understand the main ideas in complex texts on any topic, and be able to communicate fluently. Effective English language learning program tried to create independently, but we focus on the 4 most popular let's look.

1. Schechter's method This method of learning English "from theory to practice" based not on the classical model, but on the reverse, more natural system of perception. This is mother very similar to how we learn our language. How are the author young children gives an example of how to learn to speak - after all, no one tells them sentences, cases and speech does not explain the rules of construction of parts. In the same way, Igor Yuryevich Schechter suggests learning English. The essence of the modern way of learning English is that from the first lesson, students are given a certain task, for example, that of an interviewer learning a profession. In addition, all students are called "etudes". Play things, where they act in different roles and solve the problem they try to do. People with roughly the same level of language proficiency because communication takes place between the teacher and the student the fear of using foreign speech will disappear. This is the English language technique consists of three stages: in the first lexical units, words and phrases is given, and only then grammatical and syntactic in the second and third stages structure usage is fixed. The system has proven its effectiveness several times and is currently the most from the point of view of educational psychologists is one of the most successful.

2. Pimsler method Dr. Paul Pimsler is not only the perception of information, but itspecial thirty-minute lessons designed for reproduction developed a system. Each lesson is told by two people: our fellow countrymen and a native English

speaker. With this and special memorization thanks to technology, each student can learn hundreds of English words for each lesson and learns phrases. The essence of the lesson is told by the lecturers is to perform tasks in sequence. The undoubted advantages of the technique are its includes mobility - you can perform audio tasks anywhere possible: when you are standing in a traffic jam, on your way to work, to a meeting on the subway on the go or when you're in bed before going to bed. The downside there will be a lack of high-quality pronunciation and knowledge acquisition test.

3. The Dragunkin method is typical of the Alexander Nikolayevich Dragunkin system feature is the focus on the native Russian language when learning any foreign language. Very the author, who boldly called the English language simple, has its roots in the ancient Russian language, especially emphasizes that it goes back to the grammatical tense system. Dragunkin course students learn new words transcribed in Russian letters and grammatical constructions not to the 12 tenses known to us from school divided into past, present, future and their changes. Alexander Nikolaevich has a network of its own schools, where you can master three types of courses: basic, short and conversational. Innovative language learning from a linguist for independent learning The book "A Little Leap into English" containing the approach is offered. His using the system, you can easily understand the use of English verbs

It is important to memorize the rules of using articles and building sentences you can easily master the principles. Again, the Dragunkin method has a lot of negative reviews, they mention pronunciation and insufficient theoretical knowledge criticizes.

4. Petrov Method Dmitry Petrov says that you can learn English in 16 hours.

Studying word roots and prefixes is also very important while giving great benefits. According to one source, English knowing the 14 prefixes in the language itself is 14 It allows you to understand the meaning of more than 000 words while giving Of course, learning the 14 prefixes is immediate It does not mean knowing the meaning of 14,000 words. But precisely because of these prefixes the meaning of the word you can guess correctly and even understand it correctly you can also get

In the future, this language will definitely not lose its position and will develop. We can even say that this language is at the seventh stage of its development. The methods shown HERE can be useful to every language learner. These methods are useful not only for learning English, but also for learning other languages.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, for intermediate language learners, adopting a multifaceted approach to learning English is paramount. Incorporating methods such as immersion, structured coursework, language exchange programs, and utilizing technology can significantly enhance language acquisition. By combining these approaches, learners can cultivate a well-rounded understanding of English language and confidently navigate real-world communication challenges. Remember, consistency, perseverance, and a willingness to engage with the language are key to mastering English proficiency at the intermediate level.

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